

Bridging Gaps by Unlocking the Community Potential

Empowerment through Infrastructure and Networking

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MAIN QUESTIONS

- How can a decentralised and heterogenous community build a perspective on equitable scholarly publishing?
- What kinds of structures enable collaboration and sustainability?

GOALS

- Develop a concept for a community-oriented approach in building and organising strong and sustainable networks
- Empower decentralised communities in Diamond Open Access publishing and open scholarly communication

STRUCTURE

1. The community potential
2. Practice examples
3. A sustainable community-oriented approach

1. The Community Potential

1. THE COMMUNITY POTENTIAL

- Diamond Open Access affects different players with different aims and interests
- Decentralised infrastructures and networks
- Openness as a basic requirement for gaining common agreements
- Problems of cooperation and interaction between the various players
- Structures must be created to enable the community of practice to collaborate
- Overall aim: synergy of different network activities

communities are relevant and important

Where do you see yourself in the community?

Which communities are you part of?

1. THE COMMUNITY POTENTIAL

- Unlock the potential of communities by using the benefits of decentralised approaches
 - Every engagement is important and valuable
 - Diverse perspectives increase the range of solutions
- Decentralised approaches have weaknesses in coordination and collaboration
- Basic requirements for networks and communities: infrastructure and community building

1. THE COMMUNITY POTENTIAL

1ST GROUP WORK: EXPERIENCES IN COMMUNITY BUILDING (1-2-4)

- 1: Think about: What are your experiences in communities? We are searching for positive synergistic effects (2 min)
- 2: Search another person in the room to discuss the positive synergistic effects produced by community work and choose one meaningful example (8 min)
- 4: Your group searches another group. Present your example to the group. Agree on *one* meaningful example that you will present in the plenary (8 min)

2. Practice Examples

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

Tangible examples of community oriented projects in Diamond Open Access scholarly publishing:

- (1) Infrastructure: CRAFT-OA Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access
- (2) Networking: OJS Network of SeDOA

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

CRAFT-OA PUBLISHER’S LIVING HANDBOOK FOR DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS

- CRAFT-OA: Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
- “The project focuses on four threads of activities to improve the technical and organisational infrastructure of Diamond OA:
 1. Provide technical improvements for journal platforms and journal software.
 2. Build communities of practice to foster overall infrastructure improvement.
 3. Increase visibility, discoverability and recognition for Diamond OA publishing.
 4. Integrate Diamond OA publishing with EOSC and other large-scale data aggregators.”

<https://www.craft-oa.eu/about/>

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

CRAFT-OA PUBLISHER'S LIVING HANDBOOK FOR DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS

- Digital dynamic reference book in combination with self-learning user-experience and with the option to include interactive content
- Refers to key information, standards, tools, and training materials for institutional publishing in Diamond OA
- Developed in collaboration with communities of practice to ensure that the recommended resources are practical, current, and tailored to the needs of different user groups

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

PUBLISHER'S LIVING HANDBOOK FOR DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS

- Community feedback on design & content, sustainable editorial workflows
- The Living Handbook is aimed at journal editors, technical staff, and IPSPs
- With a user-friendly interface, structured navigation, and regular updates, the LH emphasises accessibility, openness, and reusability

The LH is a product from the communities for the communities

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

PUBLISHER'S LIVING HANDBOOK FOR DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS

- First live version (BETA):

Publisher's Living Handbook
for DIAMOND Open Access

<https://handbook.sub.uni-hamburg.de/>

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

OJS NETWORK OF SEDOA

- The German Diamond Capacity Centre *Servicestelle Diamond Open Access (SeDOA)* is founded by the DFG
- Improving the coordination and visibility of existing decentralised publication infrastructures, providing centralised information and promoting innovation (in the field of Diamond OA)
- Focus in the German publication landscape
- Involvement of the Community of Practice

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

OJS NETWORK OF SEDOA

- Focus: Open Source publication software Open Journal Systems (OJS)
- Target group: Those involved in non-commercial publishing who use or actively develop OJS (Community of Practice)
- Aim: Communicating, disseminating, and strengthening Diamond Open Access in the community

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

OJS NETWORK OF SEDOA

- Support existing institutional, non-commercial networks, initiatives, and individual scientific actors
- Identify, consolidate, and forward community needs
- Make publication structures more visible
- Better network the work of the target group
- Website to present activities, networking, and provision of materials

2. PRACTICE EXAMPLES

OJS NETWORK OF SEDOA

- The OJS Network supports existing non-commercial institutional networks and initiatives, as well as researchers and editors, in engaging with each other to promote their work and strengthen their offerings.

The OJS Network is building bridges across the archipelago.

3. A Sustainable Community-Oriented Approach

3. A SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ORIENTED APPROACH

Objective: to synthesise insights into the requirements for a sustainable, community-oriented approach

2ND GROUP WORK: PARTS OF A COMMUNITY CONCEPT (15 MIN)

- (1) How can a decentralised community be empowered to contribute to a **common shared perspective**?
- (2) How can a community be given **open structures** that are strong, binding and sustainable enough to enable it to work towards a shared vision?
- (3) How can a peer-to-peer approach help keep **scholarly communication** open and community-driven?

Choose one of the topics and discuss the question in the group. Bring your results and proposals to the plenary.

3. A SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ORIENTED APPROACH

1. GROUP

How can a decentralised community be empowered to contribute to a **common shared perspective**?

RESULTS OF THE GROUP DISCUSSION

3. A SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ORIENTED APPROACH

2. GROUP

How can a community be given **open structures** that are strong, binding and sustainable enough to enable it to work towards a shared vision?

RESULTS OF THE GROUP DISCUSSION

- Providing structure is challenging
- A structure should be flexible and engaging for the diverse participants
- Challenges:
 - What does “open” mean?
 - Can openness exclude?
 - What is the shared goal?
 - How can the structure be formalized?
 - How can funding be obtained?

3. A SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ORIENTED APPROACH

3. GROUP

How can a peer-to-peer approach help keep scholarly communication open and community-driven?

RESULTS OF THE GROUP DISCUSSION

- Peer-to-peer: How can we stay open and community-driven?
- You need overarching principles for a community-driven approach
- You need to agree on something, but also recognise differences
- Challenges:
 - What are the overarching values and principles?
 - How can the community can stay fair?
 - How can you show your commitment to the community?
 - How can communities be included?

3. A SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ORIENTED APPROACH

CONCLUSION

- Every input strengthens our community
- Your ideas will be carried into the wider network
- Shared insights inform future infrastructures and networks

Let's continue building an open and sustainable Diamond Open Access publishing infrastructure – together

CONTACT

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MORE INFORMATION

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<https://hup.sub.uni-hamburg.de/>

CRAFT-OA

<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>

SeDOA

<https://diamond-open-access.de/>